

Studies on the thermal decomposition of coal macerals. Part-II

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Vitrinite, exinite and fusinite from a high sulphur Indian coal have been pyrolysed in the range 300–800° at an interval of 100°. The comparison of the gases evolved in each case with those obtained from a phenol-formaldehyde resin derivative under similar conditions, reveals that alkyl and/or aryl ethers play an important part in the structure of exinite whereas methylene and ethereal linkages are important constituents of vitrinite while fusinite possesses a highly condensed structure.

In continuation of a previous work on the thermal decomposition of coal macerals¹ it was thought worthwhile to investigate the effect of pyrolysis on the oxygen-containing structure of the macerals. In that work, the pyrolysis was carried out at a lower temperature range (200–400°) at small temperature intervals. In the present investigation, the pyrolysis was carried out at higher temperature range (300–800°) at an interval of 100°.

Vitrinite, exinite and fusinite from a sample of Assam coal were pyrolysed at temperatures stated above and the evolved gases were analysed. A comparison of the individual behaviour of the macerals with that of the phenol-formaldehyde resin derivative was carried out to probe into the structure of the macerals as coal is considered now to be a polymer compound.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the analytical data of the macerals. The petrographic purity was measured by optical microscopy. It may be seen from Table 2 that yield of liquid products including tar is maximum for vitrinite, exinite and fusinite in the temperature range 300–400° and then it progressively decreases. The yield decreases in the order : exinite, vitrinite, fusinite. This may indicate the temperature and order of decomposition of the macerals. Table 3 gives the results of different gases evolved at different temperatures. The greater evolution of H₂S at lower temperature indicates that sulphur is held in loosely bound heterocyclic linkages which break down easily at 300–600°. In the formation of CO, exinite shows a maximum at 400–500° which shows a cleavage of arylalkyl ether. In the case of the resin the formation of CH₄ and CO is maximum at 300–600° and 600–700° (Table 4). This can be explained by the fact that at these temperature ranges the resin splits off CH₄ and CO due to reaction with phenolic oxygen when phenylmethyl ether is cleaved off forming CH₄ and phenoxy radical and the latter reacts with methyl radical and after a rearrangement CO is split off. A similar observation was made by Hodek *et al.*³ where they used different types of resin derivatives for pyrolysis experiments.

Table 1 Analysis of the macerals

	Vitrinite	Exinite	Fusinite
Carbon, %	77.9	79.2	92.1
Hydrogen, %	5.4	6.8	2.9
Nitrogen, %	1.2	1.1	0.8
Sulphur, %	3.1	4.8	2.8
Oxygen, % (by diff.)	12.4	8.1	14.4
Petrographic purity, %	92	82	83

Table 2. Yield of liquid products including tar (g/100 g sample)

Temp, °C	Vitrinite	Exinite	Fusinite
300–400	2.0	11.8	0.7
400–500	1.2	7.9	0.5
500–600	0.8	5.6	0.3
600–700	0.7	4.8	0.1
700–800	0.5	4.1	–

Table 4 also shows that maximum amount of benzene is also available at the above temperature ranges. This is also due to the cleavage of aryl-alkyl-etheral bridges. Similarly, in case of macerals, the formation of CH₄ and CO at different temperature ranges (Table 3) is due to cleavage of aryl-alkyl-ethers and in some cases intra-molecular rearrangements. In case of macerals, the formation of tar and benzene may originate from these reactions. Thus, there is a similarity in the pyrolytic behaviour of the resin and the macerals. In the case of vitrinite, the formation of CO in the range 300–600° shows that methylene and etheral bridges play an important part in the vitrinite structure. The fusinite is a highly condensed structure as shown by the formation of CO at higher temperature range (600–800°). Formation of benzene is maximum with vitrinite and the resin in the temperature range 500–700° and it is not that significant in other temperature ranges. This may be due to intra-molecular reactions and rearrangements in addition to reasons stated above. This also leads to the conclusion that vitrinite may also have a polymeric structure. The above observations show that exinite is very likely to have aryl-

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Table 3 Composition of gases collected (vol %) at different temperatures

Gas	300-400°			400-500°			500-600°			600-700°			700-800°		
	V	E	F	V	E	F	V	E	F	V	E	F	V	E	F
H ₂ S	4.1	13.2	1.8	3.2	10.2	2.1	3.1	8.5	2.6	2.8	7.8	3.6	2.8	6.5	4.5
CO	0.5	2.1	0.3	0.8	2.9	0.6	3.9	1.1	2.5	0.5	0.8	3.9	0.1	0.4	3.5
CH ₄	1.6	0.9	0.3	1.1	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.1	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
C ₆ H ₆	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.9	2.3	0.5	1.1	3.1	0.7	1.6	-	-	-

V = vitrinite, E = exinite, F = fusinite

alkyl-ethers in the structural units having lower condensation, and fusinite has a highly condensed structure. Formation of H₂S is maximum in case of exinite at different temperatures showing thereby that heterocyclic thio-compounds are predominant in case of exinite. Further investigations are in progress on the kinetics of maceral pyrolysis.

Table 4 Composition of gas collected from resin at different temperature

Gas	300-400°	400-500°	500-600°	600-700°	700-800°
CH ₄ , %	-	0.5	4.6	5.8	2.5
CO, %	2.5	3.1	8.8	7.5	1.8
C ₆ H ₆ , %	-	0.6	9.2	6.2	0.5

Experimental

Macerals were separated by the density-gradient method²

The method and apparatus for pyrolysis experiment were the same as reported earlier¹. To be brief, the sample for pyrolysis was taken in a silica retort, similar to that used in Grey-King assay, having a side-tube. The retort

was placed horizontally in a tube furnace. The outlet of the silica retort was connected in series with (a) a U-tube having an outlet at the bottom (similar to tar and liquor trap as used in Grey-King assay apparatus), (b) a receiver of the gas washer type embedded in solid CO₂ and (c) a receiver also of the gas washer type, but the inlet tube to the washer going down near the bottom was of the spiral type. This washer was also embedded in solid CO₂. The third receiver was connected to a vacuum pump. The gases coming out during pyrolysis were collected in a gas receiver wherefrom samples were withdrawn for analysis in a gas chromatograph. The sample was heated from 300 to 800° at a rate of 3°/min in a stream of N₂. A methyl derivative of the phenol-formaldehyde resin was used and subjected to pyrolysis under similar conditions.

References

- 1 B Barman and M Roy, *J Indian Chemical Eng*, 1994, **34**, 173
- 2 D W Van Krevelen, *Fuel*, 1957, **36**, 321
- 3 W Hodek, J Kirschstein and K H Van Heak, *Fuel*, 1991, **70**, 424